

Modelling Artificial Damage in Carbon Fibre Epoxy Composites

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ABSTRACT: Low velocity impact damage was modelled artificially to allow study of the effects of delaminations and ply-cracks on residual compressive and tensile strength. Real damage from impacts was characterised using penetrant enhanced radiography and de-ply techniques. Initially, real and artificially damaged specimens were compared. The artificial damage was then simplified so that a finite element model could be used in comparison with actual artificial damage. The mechanisms that initiate failure of the specimen were investigated by varying the position and combination of delaminations and ply-cracks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre composites are of great interest to engineers for applications that require low weight and high strength. Their use in primary structures, however, has been limited in part because of concern over their ability to sustain damage from low energy impacts without the damage being apparent except under extensive examination. In many applications low velocity impacts are quite common; for example, stones thrown up from the runway hitting the wing of an aircraft, or of damage occurring during maintenance. The effect of this damage can be greater than that from a high velocity impact which creates a neat puncture of the component, especially if the damage goes undetected and grows under subsequent loading.

Impacts result in complicated damage in the form of varying amounts of delaminations between the plies, matrix cracks between the fibres and fibre breaks.

The work that we have done aims to measure the extent of impact damage and simulate that damage both artificially and analytically, with the objective of forming a model that will predict loss of strength due to damage.

We aim to reproduce the effect of low velocity impact damage on the residual compressive strength of carbon fibre/epoxy composites with the simplest possible artificial damage. This will mean that analytical models can be simpler and should also give insight into those factors which are most important in determining failure.

2. CHARACTERISING THE DAMAGE.

In order to produce realistic implanted damage, specimens were impacted and then the damage examined using various techniques. This information was then used in designing the implants for artificially damaged specimens.

2.1. Creation of low velocity impact damage.

Impacts were inflicted on plates of composite using the impact rig shown in plate 1. The plates were made of 18-ply T300/913c carbon-fibre/epoxy composite, (2.25mm thick) with the stacking sequence $[\pm 45^\circ, 0^\circ_2, \pm 45^\circ, 0^\circ_3]_s$. The impactor had a tip of radius 6.3mm. The impact energy was varied by adjusting the mass of the impactor and keeping the drop height constant, according to CRAG criteria [1].

Plate 1. Impact Rig

Plate 2. Anti-buckling guide for compression tests.

2.2. Examination of impact damage.

The damage was inspected using x-rays with a penetrant to improve contrast. This method has the advantage of allowing testing of the specimens after examination. The method is not completely non-destructive, but if the time period of the tests is not long the effects of the penetrant on the properties of the composite is minimal [2,3,4]. As radiography gives insufficient information to allow determination of damage position through the thickness some specimens were examined destructively using deply.

2.2.1. Penetrant enhanced radiography.

After the impact zinc iodide penetrant was applied to the damage and allowed to penetrate. This was aided by drilling small breather holes. After radiography had been carried out, and the position and extent of the damage located exactly, the specimens for strength measurement were cut from the plate with the damage positioned centrally.

2.2.2 Penetrant enhanced deply.

Some specimens were depled to investigate further the size and geometry of the damage. The 'unstacking' of the plies enables through-the-thickness information to be gained. Specimens were heated to 418°C in an argon atmosphere to deply the specimen by removing the matrix [5]. This allowed the plies to be unstacked, revealing fibre breaks in each ply and, from the stain of the penetrant, where the delamination had been. A mapping of this damage for a 7 joule impact is shown in figure 1. In this map the damage recorded is that which is visible from the top of each ply as the one above is removed. The area of delamination is estimated and the length of fibre breaks measured. Matrix cracks were recorded but not measured.

(Thick line = fibre crack, thin line = matrix crack, dotted line = edge of delamination)

Figure 1 Mapping of actual 7 joule impact damage by deply using gold-chloride penetrant.

3. PREPARATION OF ARTIFICIALLY DAMAGED SPECIMENS.

Between the extremes of no damage and actual impact damage various levels of implanted damage were used. The maximum implanted damage was a copy of the real damage in terms of the ply-cracks and areas of delamination between plies, but with the shapes simplified. Since we aimed to use finite element methods to predict the effect of artificial damage, we reduced the implants to a level that subsequently could be modelled easily and efficiently, while still behaving in a manner similar to real damage.

3.1. Description of damage.

Figure 1 shows that the majority of the damage is near the back surface of the coupon. The greatest areas of delamination is between the 0° plies and the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies. Other work has shown that the largest delamination is the one that will tend to grow, so we need to concentrate on the largest delaminations which are usually those next to the lowest set of 0° plies.

3.2. Implanting damage.

The greatest level of artificial damage used implants of PTFE film of similar area to the real damage, 25mm wide. Ply cracks were simulated by cutting the fibre in the lowest three 0° plies to a width of 25mm. Given the importance of the delaminations near the back surface, our next level of damage was a pair of delaminations either side of the bottom 0° with a ply crack extending through the three plies. We also had specimens with single delaminations and ply crack only. The inserts used for delaminations were 25mm square $10\mu\text{m}$ thick PTFE film (single layer) placed centrally. For ply-cracks the carbon fibre was cut centrally across the 0° plies to a width of 25mm. Test coupons 50mm by 250mm were cut from the plates. End tabs of soft aluminium were attached using Redux 403, a room temperature cure adhesive.

4. TESTS

4.1. Residual strengths.

The specimens were tested in compression and tension to determine residual strength after damage. In all cases the results are for specimens that broke within the central section. In compressive tests an anti-buckling guide was used which had a window above the implanted damage, to allow local buckling above the delamination (See plate 2.).

4.2. Stepped loading with radiography

Since the delaminations will have a greater effect in compression by allowing local buckling we were interested in measuring the growth of damage with loading, as the size of the buckle might control the failure load of the 0° below the surface. Stepped loading tests were therefore carried out in compression, with penetrant enhanced radiography between loading stages to investigate the growth of the delamination under load. In order to open the damage to allow the zinc iodide to penetrate, the specimen was loaded in tension first. The loading steps were determined by loading the specimen until acoustic emission indicated an increase in the damage in the specimen. The specimen was removed from load, injected with the penetrant and x-rayed. The film was developed immediately and if all was well the specimen was replaced for further loading. Five to seven stages

were usually necessary before the specimen failed. This gives information about the growth of the delamination(s) and ply cracks.

4.3. Investigating out of plane displacements.

No indication can be gained from the x-rays of the behaviour of particular plies out of plane. Therefore, a few of the specimens were injected with a quick setting adhesive to determine the position of the plies just before failure. Adhesive was mixed and injected into the local buckle using a syringe while the specimen was held at 85% of failure load. Once the adhesive had cured the specimen was sectioned, polished, and micrographs taken. (See plates 3 and 4.)

Plate 3 Micrograph of section through centre line of buckle - cut along 0°.

Plate 4 Micrograph of section through centre line of buckle - cut along 90°.

5. RESULTS

Before looking at the values for the strengths of different specimens it is worth commenting on some observations made during testing. In all cases where a delamination was present at the start a local buckling of the $\pm 45^\circ$ outer plies occurred at relatively low load. The 0° plies below also buckled out at relatively low loads as could be inferred by the presence of a ridge on the buckle. The exact position of these hidden plies was confirmed as previously described. The micrographs show that the plies buckle at the crack and that a matrix crack along the edges of the delamination is formed starting at the ends of the ply crack. The X-rays of the stepped loading clearly show this. (Figure 3)

5.1. Failure loads.

Figure 2. Ultimate Strength of specimens in compression and tension.

From the results shown in figure 2 we can see the effects of the damage on the strength. The tensile failure loads are higher than the compressive and are less affected by damage; a 30% reduction in strength for real damage compared to the reduction of 70% in compressive strength. The compressive strength falls very quickly as delamination damage is increased and the highest level of artificial damage gives a very close compressive result to real damage.

5.2. Stepped loading with radiography

Figure 3 shows the results of x-ray inspection of a specimen during loading. The solid lines indicate the position of penetrant and therefore the presence of a crack or the edge of a delamination. The tensile load opens the crack where the fibres have been cut. A matrix crack along the side of the delamination is also initiated at the ply-crack tips. Note that the direction of growth of the delamination is at 90° to the applied load. This agrees with finite element calculations in other work [6,7,8,9].

Dotted lines show position of crack and double delamination.

Figure 3. Growth of delamination under compressive loading.

5.3. Out of plane displacements.

The cut 0° plies have, as a whole, buckled out and are therefore no longer carrying load. The delamination has already grown beyond the end of the crack and so the fibres have separated along the length from the rest of the ply.

6. DISCUSSION

6.1. Modes of failure in tension

Increasing the delamination area has little effect on the strength - as expected because the loading will tend to close the delamination if there are no ply cracks. If there are ply cracks there is the possibility of propagation of a delamination by mode 2. The result of this would be a split in the specimen to the end tabs with the unbroken plies still carrying the load. How this affects the result will depend on whether or no the specimen fails before the damage reaches the end tabs.

The reduction in strength depends on net cross-section of 0° fibres - for a specimen with 3 plies cut by 25mm there is a 15% reduction in the cross section 0° fibres and the strength is reduced

by 12%. In the real damaged specimen the deply indicates 25% of the 0° fibres were broken: the strength is reduced by 30%.

6.2. Modes of failure in compression.

As found in previous work the consequences of impact damage are more serious under compression loading than tensile loading. The most significant form of damage in compression is delamination. The delamination caused by impact is often concentrated toward the rear surface, and thus if local buckling occurs in the $\pm 45^\circ$ outer plies the 0° plies below are free to buckle out. If there are no delaminations the ply cracks do not affect the strength, but once delaminations cause local buckling the 0° plies are no longer constrained from moving out of plane. The buckling of these 0° plies means that the load is shifted to the remaining plies and the load path is no longer through the centre line of the specimen. If there is any damage in the next layer these may also buckle out locally. Eventually the remaining plies fail as the specimen as a whole buckles.

The buckling of 0° plies does not initiate failure of the specimen by a sudden shift of load to the remaining plies that takes them past the failure load (too little load is transferred). The buckling load for those parts of the 0° plies that are free to buckle is much lower than the failure load of the specimen, (and this was confirmed by a finite element analysis of the part of the specimen under the local buckle) though this may still be a factor in specimens with larger amounts of damage.

6.3. Delamination growth.

The load at which local buckling occurs depends crucially on the constraints on the plies. If there is a delamination further from the surface than the cut 0° plies they are free to buckle out as soon as the surface layer buckles.

The size of the delamination is also important and for this reason the growth of delaminations during compressive loading (and fatigue loading with a compressive component) means that even low energy impacts can lead to serious reductions in the strength of structures. Other work has shown that there is a threshold value for impact energy below which delaminations are not formed. There is also a value above which the predominate mode of damage is fibre breakage. This means that the compression after impact strength does not decrease much as the impact energy is increased above about 7 joules. However if delaminations can grow, the strength will be reduced so that even a small amount of initial damage can become significant. Further work to determine a more accurate and predictive model that can be applied generally is needed.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In our tests delaminations have little effect on the tensile strength.

The tensile strength depend on the net cross section of undamaged 0° fibres.

If there are no delaminations the ply cracks do not affect the compressive strength. If there are delaminations the 0° plies will buckle more easily if they are broken and so allow further delamination.

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